

Beyond the Immediate Crisis: The Economic Costs of Hosting Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

This study uses an ARDL model to evaluate both the short- and long-term implications of the Rohingya refugee issue on Bangladesh's economic growth. Although Bangladesh's GDP has continued to grow steadily, the financial strain of providing for refugees threatens the long-term viability of the nation's development. The results show that while there have been short-term economic benefits from the Rohingya refugee crisis in Bangladesh, there are also serious long-term issues. Due to temporary employment creation and higher consumer demand, the immigrant population has temporarily boosted local economies. But as time has gone on, the burden on public services, infrastructure, and government resources has led to a rise in inequality, heightened competition for jobs, and pressure on public services. These elements have impeded long-term economic expansion. Because of the increased demand from the refugee population, which is made worse by the refugee crisis, important variables including labor force participation and educational spending were found to decrease long-term growth. While the economy shows some resilience, with a 61% rate of adjustment to shocks, long-term negative impacts are expected to outweigh any temporary gains. The analysis highlights that Bangladesh's economic resilience allows for a relatively quick adjustment to shocks, but without major reforms, the long-term adverse effects will persist. The study emphasizes the need for policies focused on refugee repatriation, international aid, infrastructure investment, and labor market reforms to mitigate these challenges and promote sustainable economic development

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ملخص

تستخدم هذه الدراسة نموذج الانحدار الذاتي للإبطاء الموزع لتقييم الآثار القصيرة والطويلة الأجل لقضية لاجئي الروهينجا على النمو الاقتصادي في بنغلاديش. وبالرغم من أن الناتج المحلي الإجمالي لبنغلاديش يستمر بالنمو بشكل مطرد، إلا أن العبء المالي الناجم عن توفير احتياجات اللاجئين يهدد استمرار تنمية البلاد على المدى الطويل. تظهر النتائج أنه رغم وجود فوائد اقتصادية قصيرة الأجل لأزمة لاجئي الروهينجا في بنغلاديش، إلا أن هناك مشاكل خطيرة على المدى الطويل. فنظرا للزيادة المؤقتة في فرص العمل وارتفاع الطلب الاستهلاكي، ساهم السكان اللجئون في تنشيط الاقتصادات المحلية بشكل مؤقت. لكن مع مرور الوقت، أدى العبء الواقع على الخدمات العامة والبنية التحتية وموارد الحكومة إلى تزايد فجوة التفاوت، وتزايد المنافسة على الوظائف، وزيادة الضغط على الخدمات العامة. وقد شكلت هذه العوامل عائقا أمام التوسع الاقتصادي على المدى الطويل. حيث أدت زيادة الطلب الناتجة عن السكان اللاجئين، والتي تفاقمت بفعل أزمة اللاجئين، إلى تراجع بعض المتغيرات الهامة مثل مشاركة القوى العاملة والإنفاق على التعليم، مما أدى إلى انخفاض وتيرة النمو على المدى الطويل. ورغم أن الاقتصاد يظهر قدرا من الصمود، بمعدل تكيف مع الصدمات يبلغ 61%، إلا أن الآثار السلبية طويلة الأمد يتوقع أن تتجاوز المكاسب المؤقتة. ويبرز التحليل أن قدرة الاقتصاد البنغلاديشي على الصمود تتيح له التكيف السريع نسبيا مع الصدمات، ولكن من دون تنفيذ إصلاحات أساسية، ستبقى الآثار السلبية على المدى الطويل قائمة. وتؤكد الدراسة على ضرورة إرساء سياسات تركز على عودة اللاجئين إلى وطنهم، والمعونة الدولية والاستثمار في البنية التحتية وإصلاح سوق العمل، من أجل التخفيف من هذه التحديات وتعزيز التنمية الاقتصادية المستدامة.

RESUME

Cette étude utilise un modèle ARDL pour évaluer les implications à court et à long terme de la question des réfugiés rohingyas sur la croissance économique du Bangladesh. Bien que le PIB du Bangladesh ait continué à croître régulièrement, la pression financière liée à la prise en charge des réfugiés menace la viabilité à long terme du développement du pays. Les résultats montrent que si la crise des réfugiés rohingyas au Bangladesh a eu des retombées économiques à court terme, elle pose également de graves problèmes à long terme. Grâce à la création d'emplois temporaires et à l'augmentation de la demande des consommateurs, la population immigrée a temporairement stimulé les économies locales. Mais au fil du temps, la charge qui pèse sur les services publics, les infrastructures et les ressources gouvernementales a entraîné une augmentation des inégalités, une concurrence accrue pour les emplois et une pression sur

les services publics. Ces éléments ont entravé l'expansion économique à long terme. En raison de la demande accrue de la population réfugiée, aggravée par la crise des réfugiés, il a été constaté que des variables importantes telles que la participation à la population active et les dépenses d'éducation diminuaient la croissance à long terme. Bien que l'économie fasse preuve d'une certaine résilience, avec un taux d'ajustement aux chocs de 61 %, les effets négatifs à long terme devraient l'emporter sur les gains temporaires. L'analyse souligne que la résilience économique du Bangladesh permet un ajustement relativement rapide aux chocs, mais qu'en l'absence de réformes majeures, les effets négatifs à long terme persisteront. L'étude souligne la nécessité de politiques axées sur le rapatriement des réfugiés, l'aide internationale, l'investissement dans les infrastructures et les réformes du marché du travail pour atténuer ces défis et promouvoir un développement économique durable.

1. Introduction

The influx of Rohingya refugees into Bangladesh has had a profound and multidimensional impact on the nation, particularly in economic terms. Bangladesh, a developing country with limited resources, has long faced numerous socio-economic challenges (Talukder, 2022). Since August 2017, the country has hosted nearly a million Rohingya refugees fleeing persecution and violence in Myanmar's Rakhine State, further straining these limited resources. Despite Bangladesh's remarkable humanitarian efforts in providing shelter to the Rohingya population, the economic burden of sustaining such a large number of refugees has been significant (UNHCR, 2022; Islam, 2021).

The Rohingya situation is not new in Bangladesh. Since the late twentieth century, the country has seen successive waves of Rohingya refugees, with the largest numbers arriving in 1978 and 1991-92. However, the 2017 flood, which saw over 742,000 Rohingya cross the border in a short span, is still the greatest in history. As of 2023, approximately 965,000 Rohingya refugees are sheltered in 33 temporary camps in the Cox's Bazar region, with over 100,000 children born there since 2017 (IOM, 2023). This vast migration has caused demographic shifts in southeastern Bangladesh, as well as a slew of economic, environmental, and social issues that require immediate response (Köppl & Schratzenstaller, 2024; Rahman et al., 2022; Saha, 2022).

The Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh has serious economic repercussions, from resource depletion to mounting pressure on labor markets, government services, and the environment. The majority of refugees reside in Cox's Bazar, which was already experiencing economic instability because of its heavy reliance on tourism and agriculture (Lubna & Saha, 2024). Both the host and refugee populations have suffered greatly as a result of the unanticipated population surge, which has placed a tremendous burden on the local infrastructure, economy, and natural resources (Mahmood & Ahsan, 2023; World Bank, 2023).

The basic needs of the Rohingya refugees, such as food, shelter, medical treatment, and education, continue to be largely funded by Bangladesh. According to estimates, the country spends between \$800 million and \$1 billion each year to sustain its refugee population. This is a considerable investment for Bangladesh, where per capita income was \$2,765 in 2024 (World Bank, 2023).

Financial support has been given by international aid agencies like the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and other NGOs. But this assistance has been patchy and insufficient. The financial imbalance has put more strain on Bangladesh's national resources as the world's attention is split between several refugee crises. As a result, the nation has had trouble directing funds toward other crucial areas including infrastructure improvement, reducing poverty, and providing healthcare for its own people (UNHCR, 2023; ICG, 2023). In order to mitigate the long-term socioeconomic effects on Bangladesh and provide proper care for the refugee population, this circumstance emphasizes the critical need for ongoing international financial assistance.

International aid groups, including the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and several non-governmental organizations (NGOs), have contributed financial help. However, this support has been uneven and insufficient. With global attention split between several refugee crises around the world, the financing vacuum has put further strain on Bangladesh's state resources. As a result, the country has struggled to allocate resources to other critical sectors such as infrastructure development, poverty reduction, and healthcare for its inhabitants (UNHCR, 2023; ICG, 2023).

The Rohingya refugee crisis has had one of the most direct effects on the local labor markets in Cox's Bazar and the neighboring areas. Earnings for low-skilled workers in the host community have decreased as a result of the significant influx of refugees, many of whom are willing to labor for lower rates. A study by Ullah et al. (2021) claims that the availability of inexpensive labor has caused local workers' wages to be suppressed, especially in industries like construction, agriculture, and informal employment. Since many households in the area were already barely making ends meet, this has made poverty levels even worse.

Figure 1: Trend of GDP per capita growth and Rohingya Refugee in Bangladesh during study period.

The influx of refugees has also increased competition for jobs, particularly in the informal sector, where many Rohingya have found work despite the restrictions on their legal right to work in Bangladesh. The rise in labor supply has led to a reduction in wages, with local workers experiencing a 24% decline in income since the refugee crisis began (Khatri, 2022). This decline in wages is particularly concerning given Bangladesh's recent history of robust economic growth, with GDP increasing by more than 6% annually. The impact of the refugee crisis on wages has slowed this growth, particularly in the affected regions.

Along with the economic effects on wages and labor markets, the Rohingya refugee crisis has seriously harmed the environment in the Cox's Bazar area. Approximately 2283 hectares of forest reserve land and

1,500 hectares of wildlife habitat have been destroyed as a result of the quick setup of temporary camps (Hassan et al., 2018). The local ecology has been negatively impacted by this deforestation, which has increased susceptibility to landslides and flooding, decreased biodiversity, and eroded soil.

Economic repercussions have also resulted from the refugee camps' environmental damage. The amount of timber and other natural resources that local residents depend on for their livelihoods has decreased as a result of the loss of forest regions. Additionally, local tourism, which is a major source of revenue for many Cox's Bazar people, has been impacted by the loss of wildlife habitat. The potential for tourism-driven economic growth declines as the region's natural beauty deteriorates, thereby restricting the economic opportunities accessible to the host towns.

The study is significant because it offers insight on the complex issues presented by one of the world's major refugee crises. The report provides policymakers with critical insights into how the presence of over a million migrants has stressed labor markets, environmental resources, public services, and infrastructure. It underlines the critical need for specific policies and long-term solutions to manage these pressures, such as relocation initiatives like Bhasan Char.

By assessing the impact on Bangladesh's economic stability and development trajectory, the report highlights potential threats to the country's growth and poverty-reduction initiatives while also laying the groundwork for foreign financial assistance (Eğri et al., 2024). Humanitarian organizations, such as the United Nations and international non-governmental organizations (NGOs), can benefit from the study's extensive analysis by informing resource allocation and long-term strategy for successful aid distribution. The study also underscores the enormous environmental degradation caused by refugee camps, which has an impact on local residents' livelihoods and poses risks to industries such as tourism.

The influx of Rohingya refugees has had a severe negative economic impact on Bangladesh. Key challenges include rising living costs, regional employment crises, and lower daily wages (Ahmad & Naeem, 2020). The tourism industry has sustained significant losses, particularly in Cox's Bazar (Ahmad & Naeem, 2020; Yilmaz & Talukder, 2019; Islam

& Rahman, 2023). Government spending on health and security has increased since 2017 (Ahmad & Naeem, 2020). Environmental devastation, deforestation, and land acquisition have sparked conflict between refugees and host communities (Zahed, 2023; Haq et al., 2024). Shortages of international funding intensify these effects (Zahed, 2023). To solve these issues, appropriate repatriation procedures are required (Ahmad & Naeem, 2020). The international community must step in to end the crisis and help Bangladesh recover (Yilmaz & Talukder, 2019).

The refugee issue has a considerable influence on food security and prices in host communities. A study on the Rohingya influx in Bangladesh discovered that overall food costs increased by 8%, with protein and vegetable prices jumping by 7% and 36%, respectively (Alam et al., 2022). The impact of refugee inflows on local food security is unevenly distributed (Mabiso et al., 2014). To address these difficulties, land use planning and land banks play critical roles in improving refugees' food security. These initiatives provide access to arable land, diversify livelihoods, build infrastructure, protect land rights, and encourage responsible resource management (Nimko, 2023). As the worldwide refugee crisis worsens, applying these ideas becomes increasingly critical for assisting displaced communities and ensuring their long-term viability. The study emphasizes the need to foster self-sufficiency and economic empowerment among refugee populations worldwide.

The study provides unique insights and major contributions by focusing on the economic ramifications for a developing country like Bangladesh, which struggles to handle such a huge refugee population due to limited resources and infrastructure. It provides a detailed study of the consequences on economic growth, as well as an examination of the short and long-term implications. The analysis includes environmental deterioration caused by refugee camps, such as deforestation and resource depletion, and connects these difficulties to long-term economic effects, such as decreased agricultural output and tourism potential. Furthermore, the study's policy-oriented approach makes specific recommendations for resource management, economic sustainability, and international collaboration, while its long-term perspective on the financial sustainability of refugee support provides a framework for understanding how the continued presence of refugees may strain Bangladesh's economy. This study is an important contribution to refugee studies and

policy formulation in refugee-hosting countries since it addresses the long-term viability of the economy.

Several studies have investigated the impact of Rohingya refugees on Bangladesh, focusing on various dimensions such as environmental degradation affecting agriculture and local ecosystems (Sakamoto et al., 2024), depletion of natural resources and deforestation (Zahed, 2023), a decrease in raw materials and biodiversity (Sarkar et al., 2023), and an increase in living costs and inflationary pressures (Islam, 2021). However, this study stands out by investigating the broader macroeconomic consequences of the refugee crisis, since earlier research has mainly focused on specific areas of Bangladesh's issues using micro or primary data. Bangladesh, a densely populated country suffering with poverty, hunger, food insecurity, and other security problems, has faced new challenges as a result of the Rohingya crisis throughout the previous five decades, notably in the last ten years. This crisis has further stressed the country's economy, increasing both domestic and foreign pressures and demanding a variety of governmental actions to ensure the country's general well-being.

This work provides several important contributions to the literature. 1) The study presents a targeted analysis of how the Rohingya refugee flow is affecting a developing nation's economy, specifically via the lens of GDP growth. 2) This study is innovative in that it uses the ARDL model to provide an econometric method that captures both the short-term and long-term effects of the refugee influx on GDP. This contrasts with much of the previous literature, which generally studies either short-term implications or employs simpler models. 3) The findings are likely to help governments balance humanitarian responsibilities with long-term economic development. This is significant in nations like Bangladesh, where resources are scarce and long-term economic stability is essential. 4) The paper is one of the first to provide an empirical examination of the economic effects of the Rohingya refugee crisis in Bangladesh, employing a model appropriate to the country's economic setting.

Methodologically, we use Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimate approaches to investigate both short- and long-term correlations and causal dynamics between variables. This study is important given the need for long-term economic development, proper use of domestic resources, and effective policymaking.

Our study is unique in that it scientifically analyzes the various implications of the refugee crisis on Bangladesh's economy. We hope to reconcile the interplay between economic growth and the refugee issue in the developmental trajectory by examining the intrinsic dynamics of each. Finally, our study provides a theoretical foundation for addressing Rohingya refugee difficulties while also promoting economic development in Bangladesh, providing practical insights to help the country's sustainable development initiatives.

Figure 1 depicts a dual-axis trend graph of Bangladesh's GDP per capita growth (solid line, left Y-axis) versus the number of Rohingya refugees (dashed line, right Y-axis) from 1991 to 2021. GDP per capita growth varies over time, with major peaks in the mid-1990s, mid-2000s, and late 2010s, followed by a severe drop about 2020, most likely caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The Rohingya refugee population remained relatively low and stable until 2017, when it skyrocketed following the mass migration from Myanmar, reaching over 900,000 in 2019. Despite the enormous number of refugees, Bangladesh's GDP per capita growth has remained generally positive, while there have been swings that might be attributed to key events such as the refugee crisis and pandemic. This comparison investigates the possible impact of the refugee crisis on the country's economic performance.

Using time series data from 1991 to 2022, this study seeks to validate proven relationships in the Bangladeshi context and investigates the consequences of Rohingya refugees on the Bangladeshi economy. Notable is the discovery of the impact of new variables such as trade openness, labor force participation rate, government educational spending, and gross capital creation.

Background and current status of Rohingya refugee crisis in Bangladesh

The Rohingya problem has its roots in colonialism and Myanmar's complicated ethnopolitical terrain. For decades, the Rohingya, a Muslim minority in predominately Buddhist Myanmar, have called Rakhine State home. However, their position has been a source of controversy for decades. Despite their historical presence, the Rohingya have been systematically marginalized, being refused citizenship under Myanmar's 1982 Citizenship Law. This law effectively rendered them stateless by

classifying them as "foreigners" and excluding them from the country's officially recognized ethnic groups (Leider, 2018).

For decades, the Rohingya have faced occasional bouts of violence and persecution, which are often fueled by ethnic and religious conflicts. Significant outbreaks of violence occurred in 1978, 1991-1992, and 2012, with substantial numbers of Rohingya fleeing to Bangladesh each time (Saha, 2025; Milton et al. 2017). However, the situation became severe in August 2017, when Myanmar's military started a savage crackdown in response to an attack on police positions by the Arakan Rohingya Salvation Army (ARSA), a Rohingya rebel group. The military action, labeled as "ethnic cleansing" by the United Nations (UN), resulted in mass deaths, sexual abuse, and the devastation of Rohingya villages, leading approximately 742,000 Rohingya to flee to Bangladesh within months (UNHCR, 2023).

Despite its limited resources, Bangladesh opened its borders to the fleeing Rohingya, with the majority settling in improvised settlements in the southeastern province of Cox's Bazar. The 2017 flight adds to the already sizable Rohingya population that had fled Myanmar after earlier outbreaks of violence. By 2024, Bangladesh is expected to accommodate over 1.2 million Rohingya refugees (UNHCR, 2023), making it the world's largest refugee settlement.

Cox's Bazar, once a tranquil seaside town known for tourism, has become a massive center of refugee camps, with the Kutupalong camp serving as the world's largest refugee settlement. The abrupt rush of refugees overloaded local infrastructure, resulting in substantial humanitarian difficulties such as overcrowding, poor sanitation, food insecurity, and healthcare shortages. The Bangladeshi government, with the assistance of international organizations such as the UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR), UNICEF, and the World Food Programme (WFP), launched a massive humanitarian response. However, the sheer magnitude of the issue has taxed resources and infrastructure to the breaking point.

As of 2024, the Rohingya situation is still unsolved, with little movement toward repatriation or relocation. Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh remain restricted to camps, with limited access to basic rights such as education, healthcare, and employment. Most live in makeshift bamboo

and plastic sheeting shelters, which are prone to monsoons and landslides, exacerbating their difficult circumstances (ACAPS, 2023).

The international community, despite giving financial and humanitarian aid, has struggled to find a long-term solution to the situation. Repatriation attempts, led by Bangladesh and Myanmar, have continually stopped due to the Rohingya's dread of returning to Myanmar, where they suffer ongoing persecution and a lack of citizenship rights. In 2018 and 2019, repatriation attempts failed when no Rohingya volunteered to return, citing concerns over their safety and the lack of assurances regarding their citizenship status (ICG, 2023).

In 2023, Bangladesh and Myanmar agreed to resume repatriation talks, with China serving as a mediator. However, little progress has been made because Myanmar refuses to meet the Rohingya's primary demands, which include citizenship rights, security, and land restitution. As a result, the chances of voluntary, safe, and dignified repatriation remain slim (ICG, 2023).

The Rohingya's protracted presence in Bangladesh has posed substantial humanitarian and economic concerns. Bangladesh has suffered a significant financial burden, spending between \$800 million and \$1 billion per year on refugee relief (World Bank, 2023). This expenditure places a substantial pressure on a country that, despite recent great economic progress, continues to suffer from widespread poverty and resource limits.

The local economy in Cox's Bazar has also been significantly impacted. The flood of refugees has increased competition for resources, particularly land and water, and has resulted in food price inflation. While the entrance of international aid boosted particular sectors, such as transportation and retail, the overall economic impact on the host community was negative, with increased unemployment and environmental damage (Akhi et al., 2024; Filipski et al., 2019; Alam et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the crisis has had a serious environmental impact. The building of refugee camps has resulted in widespread deforestation, which contributes to soil erosion and raises the risk of landslides during the monsoon season (Akter et al., 2024; Saha & Saha, 2023). Efforts to

mitigate environmental damage have been implemented, but the scale of the damage is immense, and reversing it will require long-term investments (ACAPS, 2023).

The international response to the Rohingya crisis has been significant, but insufficient to satisfy the needs of both refugees and host countries. The United Nations and other non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have offered vital assistance in the form of food, healthcare, housing, and education. However, budget shortages remain an ongoing issue. For example, the 2023 Joint Response Plan for the Rohingya Humanitarian Crisis received only 50% funding, leaving severe gaps in relief delivery (UNHCR, 2023).

Diplomatic attempts to address the crisis have proved similarly difficult. While nations such as the United States, Canada, and the European Union have slapped sanctions on Myanmar's military commanders for their involvement in the atrocities against the Rohingya, international pressure has yet to produce major changes in Myanmar's policy. The geopolitical complexities of the region, particularly Myanmar's close ties with China, have made it difficult to achieve a consensus on stronger international action (ICG, 2023).

The Rohingya refugee crisis is still a complex and unsolved issue, with no clear end in sight. Bangladesh continues to shoulder the brunt of the crisis, offering humanitarian assistance to over a million refugees despite inadequate resources. While international aid has helped to lessen some of the burden, the long duration of the crisis and the lack of progress toward repatriation or resettlement have put additional strain on Bangladesh's economy and infrastructure.

The international community must continue to work on finding long-term solutions to the Rohingya situation. This includes ongoing financial assistance to Bangladesh, pressure on Myanmar to address the underlying causes of the crisis, and measures to ensure that the Rohingya can return to their homeland with dignity and security. Without such concerted efforts, the Rohingya crisis will continue to pose a significant humanitarian and economic challenge for Bangladesh and the wider region.

2. Literature Review

Theoretical background

Theoretical theories for the refugee issue provide various perspectives on the crisis. According to the Economics of Migration Theory, while migration can benefit host economies through labor contributions, it can also strain resources and increase competition for jobs and services, as seen in Cox's Bazar, where wages and employment opportunities have been negatively impacted by the influx (Borjas 1999; Filipinski et al., 2019). Human Capital Theory emphasizes that many Rohingya refugees have insufficient skills and education, which limits their formal economic integration and increases their dependency on informal labor (Becker, 1993; Milton et al., 2017; Aksu et al., 2022).

The Refugee Studies Framework emphasizes refugees' vulnerabilities, such as restricted legal status and limited employment prospects, which contribute to their economic precarity (Zetter, 2017; Khan et al., 2020). Finally, the Resilience Framework emphasizes the importance of adaptive capacities in both refugee and host communities, arguing for policies that promote social cohesion and improve access to critical services in order to offset negative economic repercussions (Folke, 2006; ACAPS, 2023). Together, these frameworks give a comprehensive understanding of the complex difficulties and opportunities presented by Bangladesh's refugee crisis, guiding policy actions that address both immediate needs and long-term socioeconomic stability.

Empirical literature preview

The extant literature on refugees focuses mostly on the challenges they present to host countries, generally highlighting the economic and social consequences. The predominant view is that the influx of migrants causes rising food and commodity prices, downward pressure on local wages, budgetary stress on public services, and environmental degradation, all of which outweigh the possible benefits (Betts et al., 2024; Shellito, 2016). Much of the studies is based on descriptive reports and primary surveys, which have constraints regarding data validity and model parameters (Alix-Garcia & Saah, 2010; Maystadt & Duranton, 2019). While recent study has begun to investigate refugees' economic contributions under certain conditions, a large portion of the literature remains focused on the

moral and humanitarian aspects of refugee crises, frequently emphasizing the human rights perspective and international responsibility (Huysmans, 2000; Salehyan & Gleditsch, 2006; Connor, 2010; Berti, 2015; Herlina, 2022). Furthermore, there is a growing corpus of research that investigates refugees' long-term economic integration and possible contributions to development, however these findings are overshadowed by worries about the immediate costs to host economies (Ruiz & Vargas-Silva, 2013).

The literature on the economic impact of refugees gives two opposing viewpoints. One line of research emphasizes the potential positive contributions that refugees can make to host economies, citing benefits such as increased labor supply, entrepreneurship, and the influx of humanitarian help and economic assets (Betts et al., 2017; Ruiz & Vargas-Silva, 2013). Critics claim that migrants often put a strain on public services, compete for resources with locals, and pose social and security hazards (Maystadt & Verwimp, 2014; Zetter, 2015). Jacobsen (2002) offered early evidence of the positive influx of resources that accompany refugee crises, such as aid and human capital, while also acknowledging the economic, security, and environmental concerns that host countries face. However, Jacobsen stated that if host governments can properly manage refugee populations, refugees can contribute to state-building and economic development, emphasizing the significance of deliberate policy responses to maximize the potential benefits.

Hosting large numbers of refugees frequently puts a strain on resources and infrastructure, with both short- and long-term repercussions. On the plus side, refugees can boost local investment, close labor market gaps, and promote commerce between host and origin countries (Ruiz & Vargas-Silva, 2013). In some circumstances, cash aid to refugees might result in considerable positive income spillovers in local economies, increasing consumption and demand for goods and services (Kumar et al., 2023). However, the inflow of migrants can put a strain on public services including healthcare, education, and housing, resulting in increasing societal tensions and pressure on local communities (Zhou et al., 2023). The overall impact is determined by factors such as the size of the aid package and the host country's economic resiliency. For example, Afghan refugees in Pakistan contributed positively to the labor market in the long run while causing short-term unemployment (Qaisrani, 2021). In contrast, the Rohingya issue in Bangladesh increased the country's reliance on international help and hindered development efforts (Hangartner et al.,

2021). These diverse outcomes underline the importance of context-specific ways to manage refugee influxes, balancing economic gains and reducing problems (Tschunkert, 2024).

Refugees can boost GDP per capita and government consumption, especially in West African countries where refugee inflows have been shown to have a beneficial impact (Nkwatoh & Ibrahim, 2021). In Lebanon, the influx of refugees has had no negative impact on high-skilled native workers, indicating that certain industries may benefit (David et al., 2019). Refugees frequently compete with locals for basic resources like housing, healthcare, and education, resulting in increased demand and potential shortages (Barman, 2020). This competition has the potential to worsen existing socioeconomic inequities, especially among disadvantaged populations (David et al., 2019). The fiscal balance of host nations may suffer as a result of increased government spending on public services, emphasizing the necessity for foreign assistance to alleviate these effects (Nkwatoh and Ibrahim, 2021).

The economic impact of refugees on host countries is a complicated and multidimensional subject. According to Shellito (2016), refugees can assist host countries by improving infrastructure, providing skilled labor, and bridging demographic gaps, but they also pose concerns such as pricing manipulation, environmental degradation, and social instability. Schneiderheinze and Lücke (2020) observed that in the short run, regions absorbing high numbers of migrants frequently see a GDP boost due to increased help and consumption of goods and services. Taylor et al. (2016) emphasized the positive impact of monetary aid in Congolese refugee camps in Rwanda, claiming that it generates significant local money, encourages commerce, and directly benefits companies and individuals.

Kudrat-E-Khuda (2020) and Islam and Rahman (2023) identified the Rohingya situation in Bangladesh as an economic burden, disrupting local labor markets, raising food shortages and pricing, and harming tourism. This strain has also caused health problems in nations receiving refugees from surrounding regions, including as Turkey, Jordan, and Lebanon (Saleh et al., 2018). Despite considerable international humanitarian assistance, the Bangladeshi community near the border has yet to fully recover from the economic setbacks caused by the Rohingya influx (Alam et al, 2023). According to Ullah et al. (2021), while Bangladesh's GDP

has increased, the native population's annual income has decreased by 24% as a result of the refugee influx. Gattinara (2017). Setiawan and Hamka (2020) investigated the contradictory relationship between foreign policy, refugee influxes, and their consequences, highlighting the security threats and regional instability associated with the presence of refugee camps. These studies illustrate the ongoing discussion among academics, including anthropologists, sociologists, and economists, about whether refugees are an economic burden or an opportunity for host countries.

The flood of refugees can have a considerable economic impact on the host countries. According to studies, refugee crises might result in higher housing and food prices in impacted areas (Akgündüz et al., 2015; Tumen, 2016). Refugees may partially replace for native informal workers in labor markets, resulting in mild job losses. However, natives' total employment rates in various skill areas remain substantially unchanged (Akgündüz et al., 2015). Refugee arrivals can support long-term investment, close demographic imbalances, and boost bilateral trade with home nations (Shellito, 2016). In contrast, they may put a pressure on public resources and lead to economic overcrowding. According to Ceritoğlu et al. (2015), disadvantaged groups, including women, younger workers, and those with lower education levels, are more likely to experience unfavorable labor market outcomes. These findings emphasize the broad and multifaceted economic consequences of refugee crises for host countries.

The influx of refugees can have a considerable impact on local markets, resulting in inflation and trade imbalances. Increased demand for basic items, such as food and housing, frequently leads to price inflation, reducing local residents' purchasing power. For example, studies show that the presence of Afghan migrants in Pakistan has caused inflation and economic strain, compromising local economic stability. Similarly, the entrance of Syrian migrants in Turkey initially increased prices, but the long-term consequences were mitigated by regional arbitrage (Genc et al., 2021). Furthermore, the necessity for imports to meet increased demand might worsen trade imbalances, as shown in some host countries (Lucas, 2024; Khundadze & Palmer, 2023; Maystadt et al., 2019). Informal cross-border trade may also thrive, undercutting formal trade regulations and reducing government revenue through tariffs (Mahmood, 2022). However, some studies imply that with effective integration efforts,

refugees' economic impact can be minimized, perhaps leading to beneficial long-term consequences (Maystadt et al., 2019).

While refugees may put a strain on public services and infrastructure (Shellito, 2016), they can also encourage long-term investment and bilateral trade. The effects are frequently unevenly dispersed among host communities, with both good and negative consequences likely (Maystadt et al., 2019). Infrastructure development, commerce, and labor markets are important conduits for determining these impacts (Maystadt et al., 2019). Investments in road infrastructure and increased trade with refugees' home countries can boost resilience (Maystadt et al., 2019). However, inadequate resources may make it difficult for underdeveloped countries to maintain or grow their infrastructure (Joshua, 2016). International help for refugee populations can temporarily increase gross fixed capital, but the gains may be unevenly distributed (Ruauzel & Morrison-Métois, 2017; Matlin et al., 2018). Bridging the gap between humanitarian and development programming is crucial for effective response to protracted crises (Ruauzel & Morrison-Métois, 2017).

The inflow of refugees can severely disrupt local economy, resulting in inflation and trade imbalances. Increased demand for vital products like food and housing frequently leads to price inflation, reducing local residents' purchasing power. For example, the presence of Afghan refugees in Pakistan has been connected to economic strain and inflation, reducing local economic security (Nisar et al., 2024). Similarly, Syrian refugees in Turkey originally increased prices, but regional arbitrage mitigated the long-term effects (Tschunkert, 2022). Furthermore, increased demand can exacerbate trade imbalances, as shown in several host countries, but informal cross-border commerce might undercut formal trade policy (Lucas, 2024; Oliver et al., 2024). However, good integration strategies can reduce the economic burden of refugees, perhaps leading to beneficial consequences in the long run (Tariq et al., 2024). Despite these challenges, some studies suggest that refugees can also contribute positively to local economies by providing goods and services, thus creating opportunities for economic growth and integration, if supported by appropriate policies (Oliver et al., 2024).

The impact of the refugee crisis on gross capital production varies greatly between situations, with both positive and negative consequences for host economies. On the one hand, migrants can boost long-term investment

and fill labor market gaps, potentially increasing capital accumulation and economic growth (Shellito, 2016). For example, the flood of Ukrainian refugees into Europe has increased labor supply, which, while initially straining current capital structures, is predicted to raise real GDP in the long run as capital accumulates (Caliendo et al., 2023). According to research in Kenya, an increase in the number of refugees interacts negatively with GDP, implying that the immediate economic burden may outweigh potential advantages (Wahogo & Ruigu, 2016). Furthermore, while refugee admissions have a short-term beneficial impact on GDP per capita in West African nations, they are also associated with higher fiscal constraints (Nkwatoh & Ibrahim, 2021). The inflow of Syrian migrants has had different effects on host countries' educational systems and budgets. In Jordan, the presence of refugees increased public education spending (Alshoubaki & Harris, 2019), but had no substantial impact on Jordanian students' educational outcomes (Assaad et al., 2023). This lack of influence is ascribed to government initiatives such as instituting second shifts in schools and establishing new schools in refugee camps (Assaad et al., 2023; Assaad et al., 2018). However, in Uganda, increased refugee concentrations in government schools had a negative impact on native students' English and math performance (Sakaue & Wokadala, 2022). Although the inflow of refugees may lead to a rise in the demand for public services and spending (Alshoubaki & Harris, 2019), suitable policy responses can support the preservation of educational quality for both host and refugee populations.

On the other hand, some contend that the long-term advantages of integrating refugees, such as increased productivity and demographic balance, may eventually surpass the short-term financial hardships and result in a future economy that is more resilient. In order to optimize the beneficial effects of refugee crises on capital formation and economic growth, this viewpoint highlights the significance of effective governmental responses.

This study fills gaps in the existing literature by integrating a variety of previously unconsidered attributes. There is little research that explicitly addresses the crisis's impact on broader economic indicators to ensure sustainable development, even though prior studies have mostly concentrated on the humanitarian and social aspects of the crisis. This is because a large number of refugees puts a lot of strain on the economy of a developing nation like Bangladesh. This study is among the first to

address this topic in Bangladesh in this way. Studies that measures the immediate and long-term effects of the Rohingya refugee crisis on the economy is lacking, making it difficult to assess how government policies are influencing long-term economic sustainability in order to address and ameliorate this problem and guide more sensible legislation. To fully comprehend the crisis's economic ramifications and develop more potent policy solutions, these gaps must be filled.

Table 1: Data Source

Variable	Symbol	Definition	Data Source
GDP per capita growth	GDPPG	The annual GDP per capita growth rate measures the percentage increase in a country's economic output per person, using constant local currency.	World Bank (2024)
Rohingya Refugee	ROH_REF	The Rohingya refugee population residing in the Bangladeshi territory	UNHCR (2024)
Trade openness	TO	Summation of export and import as % of GDP.	World Bank (2024)
Gross fixed capital formation	GFCF	Formerly known as gross domestic fixed investment	World Bank (2024)
Labor force participation rate	LFPR	LFPR is the proportion of the population ages 15-24 that is economically active.	World Bank (2024)
Government Educational expenditure	EDU_EXP	General government expenditure on education is expressed as a percentage of GDP	World Bank (2024)

3. Data and Methodology

Data and Variables

The current study gathered data from a variety of sources to explore the dynamics of the short- and long-run implications of the Rohingya refugee crisis on Bangladeshi economic growth from 1991 to 2022. The World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI) have served as the primary data source. Table 2 summarizes the variable descriptions and data sources used in our growth-refugee model. Pesaran et al. (2001) developed the ARDL model, which is used in this work. Furthermore, the study uses Granger causality Wald tests to investigate the causal

relationship between rural electrification and Bangladesh's economic growth, offering light on how these factors interact.

Methodology

The study used the Auto-Regressive-Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology, created by Pesaran et al. (2001), to analyze co-integration relationships among variables, preferring it over classic methods such as Engle and Granger (1987) and Johansen and Juselius (1990). The ARDL model solves endogeneity difficulties by allowing for concurrent estimate of long- and short-run parameters, as well as addressing omitted variables and autocorrelation. It eliminates the requirement to provide variable integration orders and pre-test for unit roots by assuming stationarity at levels (I(0)), first difference (I(1)), or fractionally integrated. To maintain co-integrating relevance, it is critical to ensure that the dependent variable possesses first difference stationarity. The advantage of this method is that it may be applied to any type of series, regardless of integration level. The regressors may be a mix of I (0) and I (1) series or fractionally cointegrated (Pesaran & Pesaran, 1997).

Pesaran et al. (2001) recommended that the dependent variable be first difference stationary to ensure the co-integrating connection remains relevant. Rahman and Islam (2020) also feel that any I(2) variable(s) could cause the system to crash. . As a result, efficient unit root tests are recommended to ensure that no I(2) variable(s) exist in the model. Pesaran et al. (2001) discovered that the short and long-run parameters estimated using the ARDL methodology are trustworthy and efficient for small sample analyses, whereas the Engle and Granger and Johansen and Juselius methods are inefficient and inconsistent in such investigations. According to Nguyen (2020), the ARDL bounds testing methodology works much better with a limited sample size. Another advantage of this method is that the model requires a sufficient number of lags to represent the data generation process in a general-to-specific modeling framework (Laurenceson and Chai, 2003). This results in an additional benefit of no endogeneity issues in the models, as both dependent and independent variables can be added into the model via lags. However, it is suggested against using I(2) variables to prevent system instability, which would necessitate efficient unit root tests.

Pesaran et al. (2001) state that the ARDL methodology is reliable and efficient, particularly in investigations with small sample numbers. Nguyen (2020) emphasizes the ARDL limits testing methodology's higher performance in small samples when compared to multivariate co-integration. Furthermore, the ARDL model's adaptability allows for additional variables and different lag structures, giving it an edge over vector autoregressive (VAR) models.

The study applies the Engle-Granger causality test to investigate the influence of the refugee crisis on economic growth using the ARDL approach. Furthermore, diagnostic assessments, such as CUSUM and CUSUMQ tests within the ARDL model, ensure model stability by verifying coefficient values and finding structural breakpoints, hence enhancing study robustness and reliability.

Analytical Framework

The functional form of the model is given by the following equation:

$$\text{GDPPG} = F(\text{ROH_REF}, \text{TO}, \text{GFCF}, \text{LFPR}, \text{EDU_EXP}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

GDPPG = GDP per capital growth

ROH_REF = Number of Rohingya refugee

TO = Trade Openness

LFPR = Labor force capital formation

EDU_EXP = Educational Expenditure

Econometric Specification

The generalized log linear form of the model used in the present study is given by the following

equation:

$$GDPPG_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ROH_REF(t) + \beta_2 TO(t) + \beta_3 GFCF(t) + \beta_4 LFPR(t) + \beta_5 EDU_EXP(t) + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

In Eq. (2) while portraying the constant term; β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 and β_5 are present as the coefficients of the independent variables.

The ARDL model is explained in an approach that addresses both short-run dynamics and the long-run relationship

$$\Delta GDPPG_t = \alpha_1 + \sum_{i=0}^n \mu_i \Delta GDPPG_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_{1i} \Delta ROH_REF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_{2i} \Delta TO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_{3i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_{4i} \Delta LFPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_{5i} \Delta EDU_EXP_{t-i} + \beta_1 \Delta GDPPG_{t-1} + \beta_2 \Delta ROH_REF_{t-1} + \beta_3 \Delta TO_{t-1} + \beta_4 \Delta GFCF_{t-1} + \beta_5 \Delta LFPR_{t-1} + \beta_6 \Delta EDU_EXP_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The model applies the ARDL approach to examine the relationship between variables in both the short and long run. The first difference operator is represented by Δ . The initial part of the equation, denoted μ_i , δ_{1i} , δ_{2i} , δ_{3i} , δ_{4i} , δ_{5i} , corresponds to the short-run coefficients, while the later part, marked as β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , refers to the long-run coefficients. The null hypothesis ($H_0: \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6 = 0$) suggests no cointegration, while the alternative hypothesis ($H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq \beta_5 \neq \beta_6 \neq 0$) indicates the presence of cointegration among the variables. The significance of the lagged variable coefficients is assessed using the F-statistic, particularly when regressors are $I(d)$, where $0 \leq d \leq 1$, to evaluate the possibility of long-run relationships. Cointegration is tested using critical values for both lower ($I(0)$) and upper ($I(1)$) bounds. If the F-statistic exceeds the upper critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, signaling a long-run relationship. If it falls below the lower critical value, the null hypothesis of no long-run association is accepted. However, values between these bounds lead to inconclusive results (Pesaran et al., 2001). The ARDL model is employed in the following equation to explore the long-term or level form relationship:

$$GDPPG_t = \pi_1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} GDPPG_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{2i} ROH_REF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{3i} TO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{4i} GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{5i} LFPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_{6i} EDU_EXP_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

We use an error correction model to predict short-run parameters based on the long-term estimates. The final stage is to obtain the short-run

dynamic characteristics required for the development of an ECM. An ECM consists of two major components. First, the estimated short-run coefficients are shown, followed by the error correction term (ECT), which provides the rate of adjustment at which short-run dynamics converge to the long-run equilibrium path in our model. ECM is estimated as follows:

$$\Delta GDPPG_t = \phi_1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \Delta GDPPG_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{1i} \Delta ROH_REF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{2i} \Delta TO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{3i} \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{4i} \Delta LFPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{5i} \Delta EDU_EXP_{t-i} + \eta ECT_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where η is the coefficient of the speed of error correction term and is expected to have a negative sign.

4. Results discussion

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	GDPPG	ROH_REF	TO	GFCF	LFPR	EDU_EXP
Mean	4.111435	258.6703	32.53724	25.53115	44.82306	1.942571
Std. dev.	1.449505	329.0025	7.994413	4.540232	4.048392	0.190365
Min	1.500471	19.743	18.88983	16.89595	38.041	1.42566
Max	6.687663	952.365	48.11092	32.21373	49.537	2.221
Skewness	-.0648465	1.32867	.4270476	-.3267281	-.2689902	-.7237337
Kurtosis	1.756792	3.15699	2.248878	2.173762	1.441833	3.002774
Observations	32	32	32	32	32	32

CORRELATION						
GDPPG	1					
ROH_REF	0.4959	1				
TO	0.616	-0.0141	1			
GFCF	0.7601	0.6932	0.5433	1		
LFPR	-0.7319	-0.7088	-0.5574	-0.9081	1	
EDU_EXP	0.2348	-0.3838	0.5444	0.2522	-0.0942	1

5. Preliminary Results

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for the variables in the study. GDP per capita has a mean of 4.11, with moderate variability and a minor bias

to the left. The number of refugees varies greatly, from 19.74 to 952.365, indicating a vast variance of refugee concentrations throughout time periods. The trade-to-GDP ratio has a mean of 32.54, indicating a moderately open economy. The data is left-skewed with generally normal kurtosis. Gross fixed capital formation (capital) and labor force participation have modest variability, with a minor left skewness. Government spending on education is quite stable, with a mean of 1.94 and a normal distribution.

In addition, a correlation analysis was performed to assess the degree and severity of multi-collinearity among the explanatory variables in the empirical model. According to Babu et al. (2020), a correlation coefficient of more than ± 0.80 between two explanatory variables indicates substantial collinearity. Table 2 shows the Spearman rank-order correlation test results. Table 2 shows no evidence of significant multicollinearity or linear dependency between the estimate model's explanatory variables. The greatest correlation between any paired regressors was discovered to be 79%, which is lower than the normally acceptable criterion of 80%.

Table 2 also shows the findings of the correlation analysis. It shows a moderate positive correlation (0.4959) between GDPPG and ROH_REF, implying a plausible relationship, however other factors may influence this. A stronger positive correlation (0.616) between GDPPG and TO implies that increased trade corresponds to higher GDP per capita, and an even stronger connection (0.7601) with GFCF suggests that fixed asset investment greatly enhances economic growth. On the other hand, the negative correlation (-0.7319) between GDPPG and LFPR could indicate structural concerns, such as unemployment or low labor productivity. The slight positive correlation (0.2348) between GDPPG and EDU_EXP suggests a minor association between educational spending and economic growth.

The series' integration order must be determined before to doing the analysis. This is accomplished by using unit root tests, notably the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests, to determine stationarity. The initial analysis showed that the variables had non-zero means and non-constant variances. To solve these concerns, the differencing approach was used to convert the data series to a stationary state with constant variance and mean for all variables. We used ADF and

PP tests to confirm the transformation's effectiveness. These tests revealed that after the first differences, all variables were stationary (meaning they no longer exhibit a trend or random walk). Thus, the results confirm that all regressors are stationary, either I(0) or I(1), and none of the variables are I(2). This confirms that the transformation successfully eliminated the non-stationarity issues in the original data. This signifies that the variables' statistical variances and means remain consistent over time. The results are shown in Table 3, and they show that all variables are non-stationary at the level except for government health expenditure, which is stationary at the level form. As a result, unit root testing provides compelling evidence to support the use of ARDL as an estimation technique.

Table 3: Unit root tests

Variable	Augmented Dickey-Fuller test		Phillips-Perron test	
	Level	First Difference	Level	First Difference
GDPPG	-2.924 (0.0426)	-8.360 (0.000)	-2.863 (0.0498)	-9.894 (0.000)
ROH_REF	-0.137 (0.9456)	5.507 (0.000)	0.041 (0.9618)	5.522 (0.000)
TO	-1.943 (0.3119)	-4.519 (0.000)	-1.969 (0.305)	-4.444 (0.000)
GFCF	-1.687 (0.4379)	-3.773 (0.003)	-1.739 (0.4109)	-3.612 (0.005)
LFPR	0.006 (0.9591)	-4.082 (0.001)	-0.175 (0.9414)	-4.100 (0.001)
EDU_EXP	-3.4 (0.0110)	-6.912 (0.000)	-3.403 (0.0109)	-7.040 (0.000)

Source: Author calculations. *p*-values are in parenthesis. All the statistics include only constant.

Table 4: Johansen tests for cointegration

Maximum Rank (r)	Param ¹	LL ²	Eigen Values	Trace statistic	Critical Values	
					5%	1%
0	42	-282.00379		117.1423	94.15	103.18
1	53	-264.53333	0.68798	82.2014	68.52	76.07
2	62	-247.96986	0.66853	49.0745	47.21	54.46
3	69	-235.20162	0.57310	23.5380*	29.68	35.65
4	74	-226.37093	0.44496	5.8766	15.41	20.04
5	77	-223.44391	0.17728	0.0226	3.76	6.65
6	78	-223.43263	0.00075			

¹Parameter, ²Log likelihood. * Indicates cointegration rank.

Source: Author calculations,

Johansen cointegration tests were conducted to further examine the long-run relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables. The table 4 presents trace statistics and critical values for different ranks of cointegration. A higher rank suggests more relationships.

Table 5: Estimated ARDL Model Dependent Variable: GDP Growth, ARDL (3,3,3,0,3,3)

	(1) GDPPG	(2) Standard Error
GDPPG(-1)	-0.372	(0.114)
GDPPG(-2)	-0.0728	(0.102)
GDPPG(-3)	0.830*	(0.195)
ROH_REF	-0.00192	(0.00254)
ROH_REF (-1)	-0.00304	(0.00226)
ROH_REF (-2)	-0.00642	(0.00231)
ROH_REF (-3)	-0.00348	(0.00139)
TO	0.111*	(0.0279)
TO(-1)	-0.0333	(0.0494)
TO(-2)	-0.0909*	(0.0429)
TO(-3)	-0.137*	0.0402
GFCF	0.734	(0.244)
LFPR	-0.0195	(0.674)
LFPR(-1)	-0.559	(0.716)
LFPR(-2)	1.095	(0.608)
LFPR(-3)	-1.077*	(0.470)
EDU_EXP	-1.126	(0.887)
EDU_EXP(-1)	-2.424*	(1.091)
EDU_EXP(-2)	-2.098	(1.140)
EDU_EXP(-3)	-5.067*	(1.502)
Constant	37.96	(15.88)
<i>N</i>	29	
<i>R</i> ²	0.987	
<i>Breusch–Godfrey LM test for autocorrelation</i>	0.076 (0.7821)	
<i>LM test for autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (ARCH¹)</i>	0.132 (0.7159)	
<i>Cook–Weisberg test for heteroscedasticity</i>	0.87 (0.3521)	
<i>Ramsey RESET test for omitted variables</i>	0.23(0.8712)	
<i>Jarque-bera test for normality</i>	2.083 (0.3529)	

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$, ¹Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity

By comparing test statistics to critical values, we discover strong evidence for at least three cointegration relationships between the variables in this research. This suggests that these variables are likely to move together in the long run, and that any short-term deviations in their interactions will

eventually return to equilibrium. For a 5% significance level, the trace statistic's first non-rejection occurs at $r \leq 3$, and the eigenvalue statistic follows suit. As a result, you do not reject the null hypothesis that the data is cointegrated, with a cointegration rank of 3. This validates the long-run cointegration of the examined series.

Table 6: ARDL bound Test

ARDL Model GFCF, LFPR, EDU_EXP)	Model: GDPPG = F(ROH_REF, TO,	
Model	F-Statistics	K
GDPPG (1991-2022)	26.64	5
Critical Values	Lower Bound I (0)	Upper bound I (1)
10% significance Level	2.26	3.35
5% significance Level	2.62	3.79
1% significance Level	3.41	4.68

Source: Author calculations. *, **and *** indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively. k represents no. of independent factors.

To investigate the effects of migrants on economic growth, we identify three optimal ARDL lag lengths based on Akaike's information criterion (AIC). Kripfganz and Schneider (2022) argue that AIC may have better properties for selecting the correct order in small samples. The study's observations are made on a yearly basis, with a sample size of 29 people and five parameters. Because of the small number of observations and the need to retain degrees of freedom, an optimal lag length of 3 was determined and applied to the dependent variable and regressors using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The results are shown in Table 5.

Finally, we investigated the long-term stability of the parameters as well as the equations' short-run motions. Diagnostic tests, including the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation test, the Jarque-Bera normalcy test, the Ramsey RESET functional form test for model specification, and the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroscedasticity, all validated the estimated equation's validity. For the test, we used Borensztein et al.'s (1998) cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of squares

(CUSUMSQ) tests. M. H. Pesaran and Pesaran (1997), Suleiman (2005), and Tiwari and Shahbaz (2013) all used the same approach to verify the long-run coefficients' stability. Figures 2 and 3 show the CUSUM and CUSUM of squares statistics, and the plots of CUSUM and CUSUMSQ remain within the critical 5% bounds, confirming the long-run relationships among variables and demonstrating the coefficients' stability over the sample period. Thus, the diagnostic tests indicate that the equation possesses the desired econometric features.

Table 9 displays the findings of the Engle-Granger Causality Test, which identifies directional links among key economic parameters. It demonstrates that the flood of Rohingya refugees (ROH_REF) has a one-way effect on key economic indices in Bangladesh. Specifically, refugees affect GDP growth (GDPPG), trade openness (TO), gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), labor force participation rate (LFPR), and, to a lesser extent, education spending (EDU_EXP). Furthermore, there is bidirectional correlation between GDP growth, trade openness, labor force participation, and capital formation, demonstrating that these factors influence one another.

The ARDL bounds testing approach utilizes the F-test to examine whether there is a long-run relationship between the variables in question and to evaluate the collective significance of the lagged level variables in the model. Table 6 presents the results of the bounds test for cointegration among the variables in the equation. The calculated F-statistic of 26.64 exceeds the critical values provided by Pesaran et al. (2001), and is statistically significant at the 1% level. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration, confirming the existence of a long-term relationship between the dependent and independent variables. This finding suggests a stable and significant association between economic growth and refugee intake in the sample area. Having confirmed cointegration, we proceed to estimate the long-run relationship (equation 4) and the short-run dynamics (equation 5).

6. Baseline Results

Long run effects of Rohingya Refugee Crisis on Economic Effects in Bangladesh

To quantify the long-run effects of Rohingya refugees on Bangladesh's economic growth, the study used the conditional ARDL long-run model for Eq. 4. The long-run estimated outcomes are shown in Table 7. The results of the long-run model demonstrate that Rohingya refugees have a negative and extremely substantial impact on Bangladesh's economic growth. The estimated coefficient for refugees is -0.02416, which is significant at a 5% confidence level, implying that every 1% rise in the number of refugees results in a 0.02416% loss in economic growth. This may appear insignificant, yet it can have far-reaching repercussions over time. The significance of this coefficient at the 5% confidence level suggests that there is strong evidence to support this negative effect, meaning the result is unlikely to be due to chance.

Table 7: Estimates of Long Run Results

Dependent Variable: GDPPG, ARDL (3,3,3,0,3,3) Selected Based on Akaike Information Criteria						
Regressors	Coefficients	Std error	t-statistic	p- value	Confidence interval	
ROH_R	-0.02416**	0.009901	-2.44	0.041	-0.04699	-0.00133
EF						
TO	-0.24388	0.149239	-1.63	0.141	-0.58803	0.100266
GFCF	1.193291	0.671957	1.78	0.114	-0.35624	2.742826
LFPR	-0.91005*	0.480142	-1.9	0.095	-2.01726	0.197162
EDU_E	-17.4259*	8.760735	-1.99	0.082	-37.6282	2.776347
XP						

Source: Author calculations *, **and *** indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

This means that refugees sponsored in Bangladesh have a major negative impact on real economic activity. As a result, the highly significant coefficient of refugee inflow indicates that the flood of refugees to Bangladesh has major economic effects for growth. According to research, refugee influxes can have a major negative economic impact on host countries. Afghan refugees in Pakistan have been shown to have a

significant negative impact on economic growth in both the short and long term (Baloch et al., 2017; Mahmood, 2022). Similarly, the Rohingya flood into Bangladesh has resulted in higher living costs, regional employment issues, lower daily salaries, and losses in the tourism industry (Ahmad and Naeem, 2020; Yilmaz & Talukder, 2019). The economic costs of hosting refugees are especially harsh in underdeveloped nations such as Bangladesh, which must boost government spending on health and security (Ahmad and Naeem, 2020). However, the link between foreign capital inflows and economic growth is complex. In the long run, economic integration for refugees remains difficult, as many Rohingya face major impediments to entrepreneurship and employment, leading to reliance on charity (Moses & Kengatharan, 2018).

According to the model, the refugees welcomed by Bangladesh cause a significant decline in the country's real economic activity. As a result, the influx of migrants puts a strain on resources, infrastructure, and social services, reducing economic productivity and growth. Similar to the findings on Rohingya migrants in Bangladesh, these negative consequences are linked to economic stress, such as increased competition for jobs, higher unemployment, and pressure on public services and infrastructure, resulting in inflation and poverty (Mahmood, 2022). Socially, the migration exacerbates inequality and weakens social safety nets by diverting resources to refugee assistance (Baloch et al., 2022; Mahmood, 2022). Furthermore, the presence of migrants generates broader externalities that affect regional stability and economic prospects beyond the host country (Stakanov, 2016).

In terms of the effect of other control variables, except for gross fixed capital, trade openness, labor force participation rate, and government educational expenditure all appear to have a negative effect on economic growth. However, the coefficients of gross fixed capital and trade openness are minor, with the latter staying negative.

While labor force participation generally has a beneficial short-term effect on economic growth in Bangladesh, it exhibits deleterious implications in the long run (Haque et al., 2019). These findings indicate that refugees' negative influence on the labor market may increase the long-term negative consequences of labor force participation on economic growth.

The negative impact of Rohingya refugees on Bangladesh's economic growth may cause a drop in labor force participation, exacerbating economic difficulties (Irawan & Khoirudin, 2024). Increased competition for jobs owing to the refugee inflow may cut salaries and reduce possibilities for local workers, particularly in low-skilled industries, causing some to leave the labor market and potentially displacing local workers (Filipski et al., 2019; Ahmad & Naeem, 2020). Furthermore, the burden on public services, healthcare, education, and infrastructure created by the influx depletes resources for the native workers, decreasing their standard of living and discouraging participation, particularly among vulnerable populations. Social conflicts and rising inequality can also discourage certain people from entering the labor force (Idrish & Ahmed, 2024). As labor force participation falls, economic productivity declines, creating a feedback loop that exacerbates the overall negative impact on growth.

Government expenditure on education has a negative and considerable impact on economic growth. According to the statement, Rohingya refugee influx and rising government educational expenditures have a negative impact on Bangladesh's economic growth. While these two things may appear unrelated, they are linked by a complex web of economic and social forces.

According to previous literature, the inflow of Rohingya refugees has had a negative impact on Bangladesh's economy, raising living costs and putting a pressure on government resources. While public spending on education generally boosts economic growth (Muktdair-Al-Mukit, 2012; Saha et al., 2022), the refugee crisis may divert funding away from education to fulfill immediate needs. Government educational spending is constrained as finances are diverted to support the immediate needs of approximately one million refugees, such as shelter and healthcare (Sakamoto et al., 2024; Ishwary & Rosdiana, 2024). This diversion diminishes the effectiveness of educational efforts, resulting in congested schools and lower quality education for both native and refugee children (Hossain, 2024). This could reduce the effectiveness of educational spending, potentially leading to negative long-term impacts on economic growth.

Table 8: Estimates of Short Run Results

Dependent Variable: GDPPG, ARDL (3,3,3,0,3,3) Selected Based on Akaike Information Criteria						
Regressors	Coefficients	Std error	t-statistic	p- value	Confidence interval	
DGDPPG(-1)	-0.75701***	0.199684	-3.79	0.005	-1.21748	-0.29653
DGDPPG(-2)	-0.8298***	0.194657	-4.26	0.003	-1.27868	-0.38092
DROH_REF	0.012933***	0.002427	5.33	0.001	0.007337	0.018529
DROH_REF (-1)	0.009898***	0.001576	6.28	0.000	0.006263	0.013533
DROH_REF(-2)	0.003483**	0.001392	2.5	0.037	0.000273	0.006693
GFCF	0.0973	0.2377	-0.41	0.694	0.1709	1.29
DTO	0.261253**	0.085837	3.04	0.016	0.063312	0.459194
DTO(-1)	0.227914***	0.06004	3.8	0.005	0.08946	0.366367
DTO(-2)	0.137049***	0.040187	3.41	0.009	0.044378	0.229721
DLFPR.	0.540089	0.482331	1.12	0.295	-0.57217	1.652346
DLFPR (-1).	-0.01853	0.382471	-0.05	0.963	-0.90051	0.863451
DLFPR (-2).	1.076742*	0.469971	2.29	0.051	-0.00701	2.160496
DEDU_EXP	9.588118***	2.502878	3.83	0.005	3.816471	15.35977
DEDU_EXP(-1)	7.16452***	1.941968	3.69	0.006	2.686334	11.64271
DEDU_EXP(-2)	5.066546**	1.502141	3.37	0.01	1.602604	8.530489
Constant	37.95612*	15.88307	2.39	0.044	1.3297	74.58254
ECM(-1)	-0.61486	0.217133	-2.83	0.022	-1.11557	-0.1141454

Source: Author calculations. *, ** and *** indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

Islam and Shindaini (2022) and Saha (2023) discovered that government expenditure on education has a detrimental long-term influence on Bangladesh's economic growth, although having a good short-term impact. Ahmed (2020) found a negative link between government consumption expenditure and GDP growth. Refugee children face barriers to education due to trauma and cultural norms (Hossain, 2024; Islam et al., 2024). Long-term effects include reduced creativity and productivity (Sakamoto et al., 2024). These findings indicate that the

refugee crisis may worsen current issues in successfully allocating government resources for education and economic growth, potentially impeding Bangladesh's long-term economic progress.

Short run effects (ECM) of Rohingya Refugee Crisis on Economic growth in Bangladesh

Table 6 shows the model's short-run dynamics estimated outcomes. Table 6 shows that the model's error-correction term is very significant and suitably signed during the study period. The error-correction term has a coefficient of -0.61, indicating that 61% of the deviations from the long-run growth rate in output induced by prior years' shocks return to long-run equilibrium in the current year. It was also negative, significant, and smaller than one, indicating that the projected coefficients from this study can be utilized to guide policy decisions.

The coefficients for the first, first, and second differences among Rohingya refugees (ROH_REF) are positive and statistically significant, showing a complicated economic impact. While the long-run impact of Rohingya refugees on Bangladesh's economic growth is negative (as shown in Table 7), there is a favorable correlation with short-run growth (as shown in Table 8). This supports a dual economic narrative: in the near term, the surge of migrants boosted local economies by increasing consumer demand and labor supply, particularly in Cox's Bazar. Local businesses have adapted to meet the needs of refugees, resulting in increased demand in local markets, the establishment of new economic activities in which both Rohingya and Bangladeshis trade (Filipski et al., 2020), and temporary job opportunities for locals in refugee-related services (Filipski et al., 2019). These short-term gains provide an economic boost, even though long-term challenges remain. It is important to highlight that we are mainly interested in the long-run consequences of refugee inflows on real economic growth in Bangladesh, as economic growth is a long-term phenomenon. Furthermore, the aforementioned empirical technique is widely stressed for demonstrating long-term benefits.

MODEL STABILITY TEST GRAPHS OF CUSUM AND SQUARE OF CUSUM

CUSUM

Figure 2

CUSUM square

Figure 3

In terms of control variables, the coefficients of trade openness, labor force participation rate, and education spending are all positive and significant, while gross fixed capital formation has a positive but statistically insignificant coefficient.

The approximated findings in this study represent one of the earliest efforts to explore the economic effects of refugee influxes on neighboring developing countries. Currently, there is insufficient data to draw reliable conclusions about the winners and losers in refugee crises. Although some preliminary research based on surveys exists, it fails to capture the potentially harmful impacts refugees may have on host nations. These surveys tend to focus on broad assumptions and are often limited to humanitarian and related issues. In contrast, this study shifts the focus to the economic dimension by analyzing available macroeconomic data, acknowledging that the refugee situation is highly complex, with far-reaching consequences for a host country's social, economic, political, legal, humanitarian, and institutional systems. This research aims to unravel one key aspect of that complexity by concentrating exclusively on the economic impact of refugees in the context of a developing host country.

Table 9: Engle- Granger Causality Test results

Variables		Chi Sq	p-value	
ROH_REF GDPPG	causes	17.37	0.00	
ROH_REF causes TO		47.019	0.00	} Uni-directional
ROH_REF GFCF	causes	7.07	0.03	
ROH_REF LFPR	Causes	21.87	0.00	
ROH_REF EDU_EXP	Causes	7.53	0.066	
GDPPG causes TO		5.42	0.03	} Bi-directional
GDPPG causes LFPR		5.51	0.01	
LFPR causes GDPPG		11.24	0.00	} Uni-directional
GFCF causes GDPPG		5.40	0.067	
GFCF EDU_EXP	causes	7.26	0.027	} Bi-directional
LFPR causes TO		55.54	0.000	
LFPR causes ED_EXP		5.92	0.052	
GFCF causes LFPR		24.621	0.00	
LFPR causes GFCF		22.68	0.00	

Our findings indicate that Pakistan has faced significant negative effects from the surge of refugees, as previously noted. While the number of refugees fleeing the ongoing civil conflict continues to rise, the economic impact of these migrants on host countries remains a topic of debate and is not fully understood. One key challenge has been the lack of reliable data. To assess the economic effects of refugee inflows on neighboring host countries, we employed the ARDL bounds testing approach, utilizing macroeconomic data from both refugees and host countries. Our results are consistent with the studies of Rother et al. (2016) and Taylor et al. (2016), providing substantial evidence that refugee arrivals have notable economic consequences for host economies, both in the short and long term.

These findings suggest that the current refugee crises, at both national and international levels, will have significant implications for host countries. Finally, the study suggests that host countries could potentially leverage refugees as assets if they implement strategies to incorporate them into domestic economic activities.

7. Conclusion and Policy Suggestions

The analysis indicates that the inflow of Rohingya refugees into Bangladesh provides both short-term benefits and long-term challenges to the economy. In the near term, the presence of refugees has boosted local economies, most likely by increasing consumer demand, generating temporary work possibilities, and encouraging trade between refugees and local residents. However, the long-term impact of the refugee influx is predominantly unfavorable. Refugees' long-term presence puts a burden on government resources, infrastructure, and public services, resulting in greater job competition, pressure on social services, and rising inequality. These factors contribute to a slowing of overall economic growth, with major long-term consequences for Bangladesh's development trajectory.

Key variables, including as labor force participation and educational spending, were discovered to slow growth in the long run as a result of increased demand from refugees. This shows that, while the refugee influx provides immediate economic benefits, the long-term structural repercussions are negative to sustainable growth.

The phrase "error-correction" shows that the economy responds quite quickly—at a rate of 61%—to shocks and imbalances generated by the refugee crisis. This demonstrates that, despite short-term fluctuations, Bangladesh's economy is relatively resilient. However, without serious adjustments, the long-term negative consequences will overwhelm any momentary benefits.

To solve the issues raised by the Rohingya refugee flow, many critical solutions are required. First, effective repatriation protocols must be started, ensuring the safe and voluntary return of refugees to their home countries. This calls for diplomatic efforts and international cooperation, as well as pressure on Myanmar to provide conditions conducive to return.

Third-country resettlement options should also be considered to reduce Bangladesh's demographic and economic load.

Economic support for refugee-hosting countries is critical. To boost the local economy, the government should invest in infrastructure, support local businesses, and promote refugee-led entrepreneurial activities. This can help to mitigate the negative economic impact by increasing employment possibilities and productivity. Targeted investments in public services, such as healthcare, education, and transportation, are critical to alleviating resource constraints and ensuring that both refugees and local residents have access to high-quality services.

Another alternative is to reform the labor market. Bangladesh can lessen rivalry in the employment market by focusing on skill development and vocational training for both refugees and native workers. These improvements may also result in long-term economic growth, as trained workers are more likely to contribute positively to the economy.

The study's conclusions provide several policy recommendations. First, Bangladesh should seek international aid and technical assistance to deal with the refugee situation. Such assistance can help the country shoulder the financial burden of providing for the refugees while putting less strain on its own resources. In addition, the government must prioritize infrastructure development in refugee-hosting communities, as well as improving living circumstances and lowering conflicts between locals and migrants.

Local integration initiatives should also be implemented, which would enable refugees to contribute to the economy through official employment. Bangladesh might collaborate with international groups to develop livelihood programs for both refugees and host communities. These programs should include microfinance initiatives and entrepreneurship opportunities.

Furthermore, public service improvements—particularly in healthcare and education—are critical. Investments in these industries would not only benefit refugees but also ensure that local communities receive necessary services. This will reduce social tensions caused by perceived inequities in resource allocation.

Bangladesh should also participate in regional and international diplomacy to address the underlying causes of the refugee crisis. The international community must continue to apply pressure on Myanmar to end the war and create conditions for the safe return of the Rohingya people.

To summarize, the migration of Rohingya immigrants into Bangladesh creates a dual economic dynamic: short-term gains and long-term problems. While humanitarian aid and increased consumer demand have temporarily improved the local economy, the long-term presence of refugees has put significant strain on the country's infrastructure, social services, and labor markets. The empirical findings indicate that, while the refugee crisis boosts economic growth in the short term, it ultimately impedes long-term development.

To address these issues, Bangladesh must employ a combination of diplomatic, economic, and social strategies. International cooperation is critical for obtaining financial and technical assistance to manage the refugee situation, while repatriation operations and third-country resettlement possibilities must be addressed. Furthermore, targeted investments in infrastructure, public services, and labor market reforms are critical for promoting long-term economic stability and minimizing resource constraints.

This study emphasizes the importance of region-specific strategies that meet the various issues that refugee-hosting communities face. Bangladesh can better handle the economic impact of the Rohingya refugee issue by implementing adaptive solutions and creating economic resilience, all while promoting long-term growth and social harmony.

Finally, the study has numerous limitations, particularly because it is based on historical data from 1991 to 2022, which may not fully reflect the changing dynamics of the Rohingya refugee issue. While discriminating between short- and long-term economic repercussions, it ignores intermediate-term effects and more localized, sector-specific outcomes, especially in areas like Cox's Bazar. The study also undervalues social variables like growing tensions and labor market upheavals, which have the potential to dramatically impact economic conditions. Furthermore, the report does not look at the long-term viability of international aid or the hazards of dependency, and its policy

suggestions are general, with little specificity for region-specific implementation. Finally, the ARDL model utilized may fail to represent the complex, nonlinear connections between migrants and the economy, limiting the depth of the investigation. Addressing these shortcomings in future research might improve our understanding of the refugee crisis's economic impact in Bangladesh.

8. References

- ACAPS. (2023). Rohingya Refugee Crisis: Cox's Bazar. ACAPS Thematic Report. Retrieved from <https://acaps.org/thematic-report/rohingya-crisis>
- Ahmad, N. S. M., & Naeem, N. N. (2020). Adverse Economic Impact by Rohingya Refugees on Bangladesh: Some Way Forwards. *CenRaPS Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.46291/ijospervol7iss1pp1-14>
- Ahmed, Z. (2020). Public Expenditure and Economic Growth Relationship in Developing Countries: The case of Bangladesh. *Journal of Current Researches on Business and Economics*, 10(10 (2)), 131–144. <https://doi.org/10.26579/jocrebe.77>
- Akgündüz, Y. E., Van Den Berg, M., & Hassink, W. (2015). The Impact of Refugee Crises on Host Labor Markets: The Case of the Syrian Refugee Crisis in Turkey. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2564974>
- Akhi, A. A., Dey, S., & Saha, S. K. (2024). Do Foreign Direct Investment, Urban Population, Trade Openness, CO2 and GDP Influence the Renewable Energy Consumption? Case of Bangladesh Using the ARDL Approach. *Journal of International Cooperation and Development*, 7(3), 20. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jicd-2024-0015>
- Aksu, E., Erzan, R., & Kırdar, M. G. (2022). The impact of mass migration of Syrians on the Turkish labor market. *Labour Economics*, 76, 102183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2022.102183>
- Akter, M. M., Surovy, I. Z., Sultana, N., Faruk, M. O., Gilroyed, B. H., Tijing, L., Arman, N., Didar-Ul-Alam, M., Shon, H. K., Nam, S. Y., & Kabir, M. M. (2024). Techno-economics and environmental sustainability of agricultural biomass-based energy potential. *Applied Energy*, 359, 122662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122662>
- Akter, S., Dey, S., Islam, M. A., & Saha, S. K. (2024). Environmental Degradation and its Effects on Health in Bangladesh. *MBSTU Journal of Science and Technology*, 10(1), 28–43. <https://doi.org/10.69728/jst.v10.29>
- Alam, M.M., Sadekin, M.N., and Saha, S. K. (2020), “The impact of macroeconomic variables on the budget deficit in Bangladesh: an econometric analysis”, *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, Emerald
- Alam, A., Dutta, I., Haque, M. E., & Nogales, R. (2022). Impact of Rohingya refugees on food prices in Bangladesh: Evidence from a natural experiment. *World Development*, 154, 105873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2022.105873>
- Alam, M. M., Milton, J., & Roy, P. (2023). Review on the Impact Rohingya Influx in the Economy of Cox's Bazar: Considering Bangladeshi Financial Condition. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2023.v05i02.1793>

- Alix-Garcia, J., & Saah, D. (2010). The Effect of Refugee Inflows on Host Communities: Evidence from Tanzania. *World Bank Economic Review*, 24(1), 148-170, <https://doi.org/10.1093/wber/lhp014>
- Alshoubaki, W., & Harris, M. (2019). The Impact of Syrian Refugees on a Receiving State's Public Expenditure: Evidence from Jordan. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijbss.v10n1p11>
- Assaad, S., Kratzert, W. B., Shelley, B., Friedman, M. B. and Perrino, A. (2018) Assessment of pulmonary edema: principles and practice. *Journal of Cardiothoracic and Vascular Anesthesia*, 32(2), pp. 901-914.
- Assaad, R., Ginn, T., & Saleh, M. (2023). Refugees and the education of host populations: Evidence from the Syrian inflow to Jordan. *Journal of Development Economics*, 164, 103131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2023.103131>
- Babu, W.A., I.M. Pantaleo, and M.O. Ndanshau. 2020. Econometric analysis of the impact of taxes on private investment in Sub-Sahara Africa. *African Journal of Economic Review* 8 (1): 176–197.
- Baloch, A., Shah, S. Z., Noor, Z. M., & Lacheheb, M. (2017). The Economic Effect of Refugee Crises on Neighbouring Host Countries: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan. *International Migration*, 55(6), 90–106. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12389>
- Barman, B.C.** (2020), "Impact of Refugees on Host Developing Countries", **Das, S.K.** and **Chowdhary, N.** (Ed.) *Refugee Crises and Third-World Economies*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 103-111. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-83982-190-520201011>
- Becker, G. S. (1993). Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education. *University of Chicago Press*, 3rd Edition. <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:nbr:nberbk:beck94-1>
- Berti, B. (2015). The Syrian Refugee Crisis: Regional and Human Security Implications. *Strategic Assessment*, 17(4). http://www.inss.org.il/uploadImages/systemFiles/adkan17_4ENG_7_Berti.pdf
- Betts, A., Bloom, L., Kaplan, J., & Omata, N. (2017). Refugee Economies: Forced Displacement and Development. *OUP Catalogue*. <https://ideas.repec.org/b/oxp/obooks/9780198795681.html>
- Betts, A., Stierna, M. F., Omata, N., & Sterck, O. (2024). The economic lives of refugees. *World Development*, 182, 106693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2024.106693>
- Borjas, G. J. (1999). Economic Analysis of Immigration. In *Handbook of Labor Economics* (Vol. 3, pp. 1697-1760). Elsevier.
- Borensztein, E., De Gregorio, J., & Lee, J. W. (1998). How does foreign direct investment affect economic growth? *Journal of International Economics*, 45(1), 115–135.

- Caliendo, L., Opromolla, L. D., Parro, F., & Sforza, A. (2023). Labor Supply Shocks and Capital Accumulation: The Short- and Long-Run Effects of the Refugee Crisis in Europe. *AEA Papers and Proceedings*, 113, 577–584. <https://doi.org/10.1257/pandp.20231077>
- Ceritoglu, E., Yunculer, H. B. G., Torun, H., & Tumen, S. (2017). The impact of Syrian refugees on natives' labor market outcomes in Turkey: evidence from a quasi-experimental design. *IZA Journal of Labor Policy*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40173-017-0082-4>
- Connor, P. (2010). Explaining the Refugee Gap: Economic Outcomes of Refugees versus Other Immigrants. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 23(3), 377–397. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrs/feq025>
- David, A., Marouani, M. A., Nahas, C., & Nilsson, B. (2019). The economics of the Syrian refugee crisis in neighbouring countries: The case of Lebanon. *Economics of Transition and Institutional Change*, 28(1), 89–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecot.12230>
- Deschermeier, P., Henger, R. M., Seipelt, B., & Voigtländer, M. (2016). Zuwanderung, Wohnungsnachfrage und Baubedarfe: Aktualisierte Ergebnisse des IW Wohnungsbedarfsmodells. *IW-Reports*. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/157179/1/IW-Report-2016-18.pdf>
- Eğri, T., Çanakçı, M., & Eğri, C. Ö. (2024). Economic Openness and Growth in MENA: Evidence from Dynamic Heterogenous Panel Models. *Journal of Economic Cooperation & Development*, 45(3).
- Filipski, M. J., Rosenbach, G., Tiburcio, E., Dorosh, P., & Hoddinott, J. (2020). Refugees Who Mean Business: Economic Activities in and Around the Rohingya Settlements the Rohingya Settlements in Bangladesh. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 34(1), 1202–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrs/feaa059>
- Filipski, M. J., Tiburcio, E., Dorosh, P., Hoddinott, J., & Rosenbach, G. (2019). Modelling the Economic Impact of the Rohingya Influx in Southern Bangladesh. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/Delivery.cfm/SSRN_ID3456751_code1123746.pdf?abstractid=3456751&mirid=1
- Folke, C. (2006). Resilience: The Emergence of a Perspective for Social–Ecological Systems Analysis. *Global Environmental Change*, 16(3), 253–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2006.04.002>
- Gattinara, P. C. (2017). The 'refugee crisis' in Italy as a crisis of legitimacy. *Contemporary Italian Politics*, 9(3), 318–331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23248823.2017.1388639>
- Genc, I. H., Naufal, G., & Gahramanov, E. (2021). Impact of Syrian Refugees on Turkish Prices. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 35(1), 139–158. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrs/feab089>
- Hangartner, D., Sarvimäki, M., & Spirig, J. (2021). Managing Refugee Protection Crises: Policy Lessons from Economics and Political Science.

- Journal of the Finnish Economic Association*, 2(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.33358/jfea.112404>
- Haq, M., Luqman, M., & Ahmad, I. (2024). Capital Account Liberalization, Institutions and Economic Growth: Evidence from Selected Asian Countries. *Journal of Economic Cooperation & Development*, 45(3).
- Haque, A. U., Kibria, G., Selim, M. I., & Smrity, D. Y. (2019). Labor Force Participation Rate and Economic Growth: Observations for Bangladesh. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 59, 209–213. <https://doi.org/10.32861/ijefr.59.209.213>
- Hassan, M. M., Smith, A. C., Walker, K., Rahman, M. K., & Southworth, J. (2018). Rohingya Refugee Crisis and Forest Cover Change in Teknaf, Bangladesh. *Remote Sensing*, 10(5), 689. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10050689>
- Herlina, A. (2022). REFUGEES : A Humanitarian Program That is Beneficial for Long Term Economic Development. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kajian Keimigrasian*, 5(2), 93–103. <https://doi.org/10.52617/jikk.v5i2.392>
- Hossain, M. (2024). Risk factors associated with Rohingya refugee girls' education in Bangladesh: A multilevel analysis of survey data. *British Journal of Sociology*, 75(4), 656–667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-4446.13117>
- Huysmans, J. (2000). The European Union and the Securitization of Migration. *JCMS Journal of Common Market Studies*, 38(5), 751–777. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-5965.00263>
- Idrish, N. M. H. B., & Ahmed, N. F. (2024). Deconstructing the nexus between the influx of Rohingya refugees and the economy (Labor) in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews*, 18(1), 290–298. <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2024.18.1.0016>
- International Crisis Group (ICG) (2023). Crisis Mounts for Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh, Retrieved from: <https://www.crisisgroup.org/asia/south-asia/bangladesh/355-crisis-mounts-rohingya-refugees-bangladesh>
- International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2023). Rohingya Refugee Response: Situation Report.
- Irawan, T., & Khoirudin, R. (2024). The Impact of Human Development Index, Minimum Wage, Labor Force Participation Rate, and Open Unemployment Rate on Economic Growth. *Journal of Management Studies and Development*, 3(01), 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.56741/jmsd.v3i01.498>
- Islam, A., Mozumder, T. A., Rahman, T., Shatil, T., & Siddique, A. (2024). *Forced displacement, mental health, and child development: Evidence from Rohingya refugees*. <https://doi.org/10.1920/wp/ifs.2024.1924>
- Islam, M. N., & Rahman, M. M. (2023). Tourism, labour market, and host community impacts during the refugee crisis in Cox's Bazar. *International Journal of Tourism Policy*, 14(1), 91–106. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijtp.2024.135434>

- Islam, M. S., & Shindaini, A. J. M. (2022). Impact of institutional quality and human capital creation on economic growth in Bangladesh: evidence from an ARDL approach. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 49(12), 1787–1802. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijse-12-2021-0732>
- Islam, M. (2021). The Rohingya Crisis and its Economic Implications for Bangladesh. *Journal of Migration Studies*, 9(1), 45-60.
- Ishwary.S. and Rosdiana.H. (2024). Peran United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund (UNICEF) dalam Menangani Pemenuhan Hak Anak-Anak Pengungsi Rohingya di Bangladesh Tahun 2017-2023. doi: 10.62383/risoma.v2i3.214
- Jacobsen, K. (2002). Can Refugees Benefit the State? Refugee Resources and African Statebuilding. *The Journal of Modern African Studies*, 40(4), 577–596. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3876026>
- Johansen, S., and K. Juselius (1990). Maximum Likelihood Estimation and Inference on Cointegration- with Applications to the Demand for Money”, *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 52(2): 169–210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0084.1990.mp52002003.x>.
- Qaisrani, A. (2021). Bridging the Gaps - Migration Management and Policy Options for Afghan Refugees in Pakistan, Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung.
- Köppl, A., & Schratzenstaller, M. (2024). Macroeconomic effects of green recovery programs. *Eurasian Economic Review*, 14(1), 61-86.
- Khaled, A. F. M. (2021). Do No Harm in refugee humanitarian aid: the case of the Rohingya humanitarian response. *Journal of International Humanitarian Action*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41018-021-00093-9>
- Khan, H. T. A., Rahman, M. A., Molla, M. H., Shahjahan, M., & Abdullah, R. B. (2020). Humanitarian Emergencies of Rohingya Older People in Bangladesh: A Qualitative Study on Hopes and Reality. *Ageing International*, 47(1), 20–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12126-020-09400-y>
- Khatri, G. (2022). The Effects of Rohingya Refugees from Myanmar on Low-Skilled Wages in the Chittagong Division of Bangladesh. *UCL Journal of Economics*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.444.2755-0877.1402>
- Khundadze, M., & Palmer, S. (2023). Mass Immigration and the Effect on Employment and Prices: Evidence from the Ukrainian Refugee Crisis. *Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7939250>
- Kripfganz, S. & Schneider, D. (2022). "[ARDL: Estimating autoregressive distributed lag and equilibrium correction models](#)," [TUPD Discussion Papers](#) 18, Graduate School of Economics and Management, Tohoku University.
- Kudrat-E-Khuda. (2020). The impacts and challenges to host country Bangladesh due to sheltering the Rohingya refugees. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2020.1770943>

- Kumar, Deepak & Gupta, Anubhab. (2023). A Gendered Approach to Economic Impacts of Refugee Aid in Kenya.
- László, A., & Schmidt, M. (2018). The Socioeconomic Impact of the Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh. *International Migration*, 56(6), 145-158.
- Laurenceson, J., & Chai, J. (2003). *Financial reform and economic development in China*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar
- Leider, J. (2018). Rohingya: The History of a Muslim Identity in Myanmar. *Oxford Handbook of Islam in Southeast Asia*, 109-126. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199986467.013.10>
- Lubna, M. M., & Saha, S. K. (2024). Justification of the Twin Deficit Hypothesis in Bangladesh. *International Trade, Politics and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/itpd-04-2023-0009>.
- Lucas, B. (2024). *Impacts of Internally Displaced Populations on Their Host Communities*. <https://doi.org/10.19088/k4dd.2024.028>
- Mabiso, A., Maystadt, J., Vandecasteele, J., & Hirvonen, K. (2014). Refugees, Food Security, and Resilience in Host Communities Transitioning from Humanitarian Assistance to Development In Protracted Refugee Situations.
- Mahmood, R. (2022). Afghan Refugees: A Threat to the Economic Security of Pakistan. *Journal of Psychology and Political Science*, 31, 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.55529/jpps.31.16.23>
- Mahmood, M. A., & Ahsan, M. (2023). Economic Vulnerability and Resilience of Host Communities: A Case Study of Rohingya Refugees in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 50(1), 112-126.
- Matlin, S. A., Depoux, A., Schütte, S., Flahault, A., & Saso, L. (2018). Migrants' and refugees' health: towards an agenda of solutions. *Public Health Reviews*, 39(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40985-018-0104-9>
- Maystadt, J., Hirvonen, K., Mabiso, A., & Vandecasteele, J. (2019). Impacts of Hosting Forced Migrants in Poor Countries. *Annual Review of Resource Economics*, 11(1), 439–459. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-resource-090518-095629>
- Milton, A. H., Rahman, M., Hussain, S., Jindal, C., Choudhury, S., Akter, S., & Efid, J. T. (2017). Trapped in Statelessness: Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(8), 942. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14080942>
- Muktdair-Al-Mukit, D. (2012). Public Expenditure on Education and Economic Growth: The Case of Bangladesh.
- Moses, F., & Kengatharan, S. (2018). Bringing Rohingya Refugees off-Track Of Long-Term Economic Vulnerability In Bangladesh. *Journal of Nusantara Studies (JONUS)*, 3(1), 42. <https://doi.org/10.24200/jonus.vol3iss1pp42-50>
- Nimko, O. (2023a). Enhancing food security for refugees through land use planning and land banks. *InterConf*, 37(171), 223–227. <https://doi.org/10.51582/interconf.19-20.09.2023.016>

- Nimko, O. (2023b). Enhancing food security for refugees through land use planning and land banks. *InterConf*, 37(171), 223–227. <https://doi.org/10.51582/interconf.19-20.09.2023.016>
- Nisar, M. H., Khalid, H., Ali, J., & Khalid, F. (2024). Socio-Economic Analysis of Afghan Refugees Repatriation from Pakistan: A 2023 Case Study. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.52131/pjhss.2024.v12i1.2059>
- Nkwatoh, L. S., & Ibrahim, K. S. (2021). Macroeconomic Impact of Refugee Inflow on West African Countries. *Quantitative Economics and Management Studies*, 2(1), 36–46. <https://doi.org/10.35877/454ri.qems251>
- Nguyen, H.H. (2020). Impact of foreign direct investment and international trade on economic growth: Empirical study in Vietnam. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business* 7 (3): 323–331.
- Oliver, L., D’Errico, M., & Winters, P. (2024). Economic Integration between Refugee Settlements and Host Communities. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 60(3), 360–379. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2023.2282363>
- Pesaran, M. H., & Pesaran, B. (1997). *Working with Microfit 4.0: Interactive econometric analysis*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Pesaran MH, Shin Y, Smith RJ (2001) Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(3):289–326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.616>
- Rahman, M., and A. Islam. 2020. Some dynamic macroeconomic perspectives for India’s economic growth: Applications of linear ARDL bounds testing for co-integration and VECM. *Journal of Financial Economic Policy* 12 (4): 641–658.
- Rahman, M. M., Islam, A. K. M. N., & Rahman, M. M. (2022). The Socio-Economic Impact of Rohingya Refugees on Host Communities in Bangladesh: Evidence from Cox’s Bazar. *Asian Journal of Refugee Studies*, 5(2), 23-42.
- Rother, Bjoern & Pierre, Gaele & Lombardo, Davide & Herrala, Risto & Toffano, Priscilla & Roos, Erik & Auclair, Allan & Manasseh, Karina. (2016). The Economic Impact of Conflicts and the Refugee Crisis in the Middle East and North Africa. Staff Discussion Notes. 16. 1. 10.5089/9781475535785.006.
- Ruadel, H. & Morrison-Métois, S. (2017). "[Responding to Refugee Crises: Lessons from evaluations in Ethiopia and Uganda as countries of destination](#)," [OECD Development Co-operation Working Papers](#) 38, OECD Publishing.
- Ruiz, I., & Vargas-Silva, C. (2013). The Economics of Forced Migration. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 49(6), 772–784. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2013.777707>

- Sakamoto, M., Ullah, S. A., & Tani, M. (2024). Impacts of refugee influx on the local economy and environmental degradation in Bangladesh: A spatial multilevel autoregressive analysis. *World Development*, 183, 106729. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2024.106729>
- Sakaue, K., & Wokadala, J. (2022). Effects of including refugees in local government schools on pupils' learning achievement: Evidence from West Nile, Uganda. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 90, 102543. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2021.102543>
- Saleh, Ayman & Aydin, Serdar & Kocak, Orhan. (2018). A comparative Study of Syrian Refugees in Turkey, Lebanon, and Jordan: Healthcare Access and Delivery. *International Journal of Society Systems Science*. 10.26466/opus.376351.
- Saha, S. K. (2025). Empowering Rural South Asia: Off-Grid Solar PV, Electricity Accessibility, and Sustainable Agriculture, Applied Energy, Volume 377, Part C, 124639, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.124639>. Elsevier.
- Saha, S. K. (2024). Assessing the impact of rural electrification on economic growth: a comprehensive analysis considering informal economy and income inequality in Bangladesh. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Regional Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41685-024-00336-8>. Springer.
- Saha, S. K., Sadekin, M. N., & Saha, S. K. (2022). Effects of institutional quality on foreign direct investment inflow in lower-middle income countries. *Heliyon*, 8(10), e10828. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10828>. Elsevier.
- Saha, S. K. (2023), Does the Impact of the Foreign Direct Investment on Labor Productivity Change Depending on Productive Capacity? *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-023-01444-0>. Springer.
- Saha, S., & Saha, S.K. (2023). Informal Economy and Agricultural Productivity in Bangladesh: A Time Series Analysis. *Problems of Agricultural Economics*, 376(3) 2023, 91–113. <https://doi.org/10.30858/zer/171498>
- Saha, S.K. (2022), Sources of productivity in South Asia, *Review of Market Integration*, 13(2-3), 154–176, SAGE.
- Salehyan, I., & Gleditsch, K. S. (2006). Refugees and the Spread of Civil War. *International Organization*, 60(2), 335-366.
- Sarkar, S. K., Saroar, M., & Chakraborty, T. (2023). Navigating nature's toll: Assessing the ecological impact of the refugee crisis in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. *Heliyon*, 9(7), e18255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18255>
- Schneiderheinze, C., & Lücke, M. (2020). Socio-economic impacts of refugees on host communities in developing countries. *Kiel Institute for the World Economy*. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/222421/1/PEGNet-Policy-Studies-03-2020.pdf>

- Setiawan, A., & Hamka, H. (2020). Role of Indonesian Humanitarian Diplomacy toward Rohingya Crisis in Myanmar. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Social Sciences, ICSS 2019, 5-6 November 2019, Jakarta, Indonesia*. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.5-11-2019.2292481>
- Shellito, K. (2016). The Economic Effect of Refugee Crises on Host Countries and Implications for the Lebanese Case.
- Stakanov, R. (2016). Refugees as a factor of economic development in host countries of migration. 82-89. doi: 10.17721/APMV.2016.129.0.82-89
- Suleiman, W. A. (2005). *The impact of investment and financial intermediation on economic growth: New evidence from Jordan*. Abstract mimeo.
- Talukder, M.I.A. (2022). Are Refugees a Blessing or a Curse: An Analysis of Economic Impact of Rohingya Refugees on Bangladesh since the Exodus. In: Bülbül, K., Islam, M.N., Khan, M.S. (eds) *Rohingya Refugee Crisis in Myanmar*. Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6464-9_7
- Tariq, H., Ali, Y., Sabir, M., Garai-Fodor, M., & Csiszárík-Kocsir, Á. (2024). Barriers to Entrepreneurial Refugees' Integration into Host Countries: A Case of Afghan Refugees. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062281>
- Taylor, J. E., Filipski, M. J., Alloush, M., Gupta, A., Valdes, R. I. R., & Gonzalez-Estrada, E. (2016). Economic impact of refugees. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113(27), 7449–7453. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1604566113>
- Tiwari, A. K., & Shahbaz, M. (2013). Modelling the relationship between whole sale price and consumer price indices: Cointegration and causality analysis for India. *Global Business Review*, 14(3), 397–411.
- Tschunkert, K. (2022). *Improving the Prospects for Peace in Nigeria: Spotlight on Cash-based Transfers*. <https://doi.org/10.55163/vazh6304>
- Tschunkert, K. (2024). *The Political Economy of Refugee Integration Policies*. <https://doi.org/10.19088/k4dd.2024.021>
- Tumen, S. (2016). The Economic Impact of Syrian Refugees on Host Countries: Quasi-Experimental Evidence from Turkey. *American Economic Review*, 106(5), 456–460. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.p20161065>
- Ullah, S. M. A., Asahiro, K., Moriyama, M., & Tani, M. (2021). Socioeconomic Status Changes of the Host Communities after the Rohingya Refugee Influx in the Southern Coastal Area of Bangladesh. *Sustainability*, 13(8), 4240. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084240>
- UNHCR. (2023). Bangladesh: Rohingya Refugee Response. United Nations Refugee Agency (UNHCR). Retrieved from <https://unhcr.org/bangladesh>
- UNHCR (2024), Rohingya refugee database, retrieved from: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/country/bgd>
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). (2022). Rohingya Refugee Crisis: Global Focus on Bangladesh.

- Wahogo, G. M., & Ruigu, G. (2016). Refugee Influx and Its Impact on Economic Growth In Kenya. *International Journal of Economics*, 1(2), 61–76. <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/98856>
- Wolf, S. O. (2014). The Rohingya Crisis in Bangladesh: Security Implications and Policy Options. *Institute of South Asian Studies*, Policy Brief No. 2020.
- World Bank. (2023). Bangladesh: The Rohingya Crisis and Its Economic Implications.
- World Bank. (2023). <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/bangladesh>.
- Yilmaz, M. L., & Talukder, M. İ. A. (2019). Economic Impact of Rohingya Exodus on Bangladesh. *Liberal Düşünce Dergisi*, 24(95), 111–129. <https://doi.org/10.36484/liberal.592964>
- Zahed, I. U. M. (2023). Impact of the geopolitical status quo vis-à-vis the Rohingya crisis on the social, economic, and political aspects of Bangladesh. *Asian Politics & Policy*, 15(4), 643–667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aspp>.
- Zetter, R. (2017). Protecting Forced Migrants: A State-of-the-Art Report on the Global Refugee Crisis. *Forced Migration Review*, 55, 16-19.
- Zetter, R. (2015). Protection in Crisis: Forced Migration and Protection in a Global Era. Migration Policy Institute, University of Oxford.
- Zhou, Y., Grossman, G., & Ge, S. (2023). Inclusive refugee-hosting can improve local development and prevent public backlash. *World Development*, 166, 106203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2023.106203>